

Uses of Modern Physical Tools in our Synthetic Investigations*

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In this lecture has been described the use of physical tools in synthetic investigations carried out by us. These applications range from extremely simple cases to comparatively complicated ones, but, in each case, solved a structural, configurational, or conformational problem.

In one of the syntheses of oestrone¹, preparation of the intermediate isomers of the hydrochrysenone (3) consisted of dehydration of the carbinol (1) followed by aluminium chloride catalysed cyclisation of the resulting unsaturated ketone (2). The UV spectra of (2), λ_{max}^{EtOH} 249 m μ (log ϵ 4.2), and of its semicarbazone, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 269 m μ (log ϵ 4.5), proved at once the position of the ethylenic linkage in conjugation with the ketonic group in the unsaturated ketone and showed that its cyclisation represented the intramolecular counterpart of the very interesting hydroarylation of 1-acetylcyclohexene with benzene to give 4-phenyl-hexahydroacetophenone².

In the first step of the sequence leading to our synthesis³ of ethyl 2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-cyclopentanone-2-acetate, ethyl cyanoacetate was condensed with ethyl α -acetylglutarate to give, besides the expected unsaturated cyanoester, a crystalline byproduct, the chemical investigation of which and the UV data⁴, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 279 m μ (log ϵ 4.1), led to the choice between two formulae, (4) and (5), to represent it. IR absorption data⁴ (Fig. 1), however, showed

* Acharya J. C. Ghosh memorial lecture, delivered on September 4, 1968 at the Indian Institute Science, Bangalore.

1. W. S. Johnson, D. K. Banerjee, W. P. Schneider, C. D. Gutsche, W. E. Shelberg and L. J. Chinn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 2832.
2. C. D. Nenitzescu and I. G. Gavat, *Ann.*, 1935, **519**, 260; W. S. Johnson and R. D. Offenbauer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1045; W. S. Johnson, *Record of Chemical Progress*, 1949, Spring Issue, p. 53.
3. D. K. Banerjee and S. K. Das Gupta, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1318.
4. D. K. Banerjee, P. Sengupta and S. K. Das Gupta, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 1516.

two bands at 1688 cm^{-1} and 1635 cm^{-1} , strongly suggesting the presence of an α, β -unsaturated ester carbonyl and an acid amide carbonyl respectively. Further, it showed narrow bands at 3350 cm^{-1} and 3200 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of non-associated and associated N-H stretching vibrations respectively and this view was substantiated by the fact that at the lower concentration the 3350 cm^{-1} band is stronger, relative to the 3200 cm^{-1} band, than at higher concentration. The consideration of IR spectra excluded the structure (5).

Fig. 1

6-*p*-Anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-2-acetic acid (6, R = H) was used for a stereoselective synthesis⁵ of oestrone. Turner⁶ had prepared it earlier by a different method and assigned the structure (7, R = H) on the basis of the UV absorption maximum, λ_{max}^{EtOH} $289\text{ m}\mu$, of its precursor (8). Johnson⁷, later, assigned the structure (9) to it because the C = O stretching vibration band of the ketone carbonyl showed up at $6.04\text{ m}\mu$ in the IR. We accepted Johnson's assignment and proceeded with the synthesis. Recently, however, the structure of the unsaturated keto acid (6, R = H) has been proved beyond doubt by studying the NMR spectrum⁸ (Fig. 2) of its methyl ester (6, R = CH_3), which was prepared by the diazomethane method and showed one of the UV maxima at $288\text{ m}\mu$ and IR peaks at 6.05μ . The quartet centred at 424 Hz for 4 aromatic protons, the singlets at 229 Hz and 218 Hz

O
 \parallel
 $-\text{C}-\text{OCH}_3$

for 3 protons each of Ar-OCH₃ and -C(=O)-OCH₃ respectively, the singlet at 193 Hz for 2 protons of the acetate methylene deshielded further by the ethylenic linkage, and the broad multiplets ranging from 115 Hz to 175 Hz for the remaining 6 methylene protons are in perfect agreement with the structure (6, R = CH_3). The absence of signal for a vinyl proton along

5. D. K. Banerjee and K. M. Sivanandaiah, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 20; *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 652.
6. D. L. Turner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1284.
7. W. S. Johnson, R. G. Christiansen, and R. E. Ireland, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1995.
8. D. K. Banerjee and L. R. Subrahmanyam, unpublished work; we are grateful to Dr. T. R. Govindachari, Director, CIBA Research Centre, Bombay, for the NMR spectrum.

with the absence of splitting of the acetate methylene protons and appearance of the signal at a comparatively downfield region excludes the alternate formula (7, R = CH₃).

Fig.2

During an investigation⁹ on the synthesis of oestrone, one of the reduction experiments¹⁰ with the tricyclic unsaturated keto-cyano ester (10) involved a modified Clemmensen method¹¹. The only isolable crystalline product, obtained in very poor yield, melted at 298–301°, showed UV, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 262 (ϵ 38,720), characteristic of a *p*-methoxystyrene (CH₃O-

1634 cm⁻¹ (olefinic C = C), 1613 cm⁻¹ (aromatic skeletal), and 826 cm⁻¹ (C = C). The

UV, IR, and analytical data, the high melting point of the compound, and its insolubility in common organic solvents suggested the dimeric structure (11), presumably formed during reduction of the carbonyl group of the compound (10). To prove it the mass spectrum (Fig. 3) of the compound was studied. The molecular ion; *m/e* 620 (1.3%), arising by the loss of a non-bonding electron from any one of the oxygen atoms, is consistent with the molecular formula C₃₃H₄₀N₂O₆. The intense peak at *m/e* 310 (100%) could arise by the cleavage of the central bond of (11) to give the ion (12). The peak at *m/e* 589 might be due to the formation of the ion (13) or (14), depending, in the first case, on the loss of the methoxyl group either in one step or by the loss of a formaldehyde molecule with concomitant hydrogen

9. D. K. Banerjee, S. R. Ramadas, and G. Ramani, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 5311.

10. D. K. Banerjee and G. Ramani, unpublished work; we are grateful to Prof. K. D. Berlin, Oklahoma State University, U.S.A., for the Mass spectra.

11. K. H. Dudley, H. W. Miller, R. C. Corley, and M. E. Wall, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 2317.

rearrangement followed by the loss of a hydrogen atom¹² and, in the second case, by the loss of the methoxyl from the carbomethoxy group. The cation (14) might lose carbon monoxide to give the ion (15) which would explain the m/e 561 peak. The m/e 530 peak could be explained by the removal of $C-OCH_3$ from the cation (16) followed by the loss of

methoxyl to give the ion (17).

Fig.3

An isomer of 19-nortestosterone (23) was prepared¹³ from *d*-equilénin (18) by the method outlined below. *d*-17, 17-Ethylene-dioxyestra-1, 3, 5(10), 6, 8-pentaen-3-ol (19), prepared from (18), was catalytically hydrogenated. The phenolic fraction, obtained after removal of the ethylenedioxy group, consisted of two compounds, *d*-8-isoestrone (20) and *d*-9-isoestrone (21). The lithium-ammonia reduction of the methyl ether of (20) followed by mild hydrolysis gave the β , γ -unsaturated ketone (22), which on treatment with methanolic hydrochloric acid furnished the α , β -unsaturated ketone (23) in low yield. Djerassi¹⁴ had suggested boat conformation for the B-ring in 8-isotestosterone (24, R = CH₃) on the basis of ORD data. But, the possibility of enolization of the C-10 hydrogen in the 19-nor compound (23) under the conditions of isomerization of (22) led us to assign α -configuration to the C-10 hydrogen with the preferred all chair arrangement (23). Previously Velluz and coworkers^{15a} claimed to have prepared *d*- and *l*-forms of both 8-iso-19-nortestosterone (24, R = H) and 8-iso-10-iso-19-nortestosterone (23). Dr. R. Bucourt and Dr. G. Nomine very kindly furnished samples of their optically active compounds and we obtained optical rotatory dispersion data (Fig. 4) on all three compounds. It may be observed the ORD curve of our sample is identical with that of the sample claimed by Dr. Bucourt and Dr. Nomine to be 8-iso-10-iso-19-nortestosterone, but different from that of 8-isotestosterone (24, R = CH₃), and this confirmed the α -configuration of the C-10 hydrogen of (23). The ORD curve of the compound claimed by Dr. Bucourt and Dr. Nomine to be 8-iso-19-nortestosterone (24, R = H) was, however, entirely different from that of 8-isotestosterone (24, R = CH₃), and this compound, therefore, did not appear to have the configuration assigned to it. Later^{15b}, these workers have proved their claim.

13. D. K. Banerjee, B. Sugavanam, and G. Nadamuni, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 2771.

14. C. Djerassi, R. Riniker, and B. Riniker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 6362, 6377.

15a. L. Velluz, G. Nomine, and R. Bucourt, *C. R. Acad. Sci., Paris*, 1963, **257**, 811; R. Bucourt and G. Nomine, *Fr. 1*, 404, 413 (C 107c); *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **63**, 18212b.

15b. R. Bucourt, D. Hainaut, J. C. Gase and G. Nominé, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 5093.

Bachmann and Thomas¹⁶ and Martin and Robinson¹⁷ had prepared two isomers of each of the benzhydrindanone-1 derivatives, (25, R = H and CH₃) and (26, R = H and CH₃),

Fig. 4

respectively by following the classical procedure¹⁸ of Bachmann, Cole, and Wilds for the synthesis of equilenin. But, they did not prove the configurations of these isomers. We required the corresponding *trans*-1 β -hydroxy-benzohydrindane derivatives as intermediates for the synthesis of steroids, and, therefore, it was essential that the configurations of these isomers should be unequivocally determined. For this purpose, the tricyclic unsaturated keto esters (27, R = H and CH₃) were prepared¹⁹, starting from 6-methoxytetralone and 5-methyl-6-methoxytetralone, and saponified and decarboxylated by the method of Johnson *et al.*²⁰ to obtain two structurally isomeric unsaturated ketones, (28, R = H and CH₃) and (29, R = H and CH₃) in each case respectively. The α , β -unsaturated ketones (28, R = H and CH₃) were formed by migration of the ethylenic linkage from $\Delta^{3(3a)}$ to the Δ^2 position, leading to the stable²⁰ *cis*-hydrindane configurations in (28, R = H and CH₃), and could be immediately identified by their UV spectra which showed characteristic absorption maxima at 227 m μ (log ϵ 4.2), 221 m μ (log ϵ 4.2) and 279 m μ (log ϵ 3.5), 278 m μ (log ϵ 3.4) for the α , β -unsaturated ketone and the anisole chromophores respectively. The corresponding hydrindanones obtained by their hydrogenation were therefore assigned the *cis*-configurations (25, R = H and CH₃). The isomeric β , γ -unsaturated ketones (29, R = H and CH₃) were also easily identified by their UV absorption maxima, 264.5 m μ (log ϵ 4.2) and 268 m μ (log ϵ 4.3) respectively, characteristic of the *p*-methoxystyrene chromophore. The corresponding hydroxy compounds (30, R = H and CH₃), obtained by treatment with sodium borohydride and showing the retention of the *p*-methoxystyrene chromophores by their UV absorption maxima, 266 m μ (log ϵ 4.2) and 274 m μ (log ϵ 4.0) respectively, on catalytic hydrogenation gave exclusively the *trans*-hydroxyhydrindanes (31, R = H and

16. W. E. Bachmann and D. G. Thomas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 94.

17. R. H. Martin and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 491.

18. W. E. Bachmann, W. Cole and A. L. Wilds, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 824.

19. D. K. Banerjee, S. Chatterjee, C. N. Pillai and M. V. Bhatt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3769.

20. W. S. Johnson, J. W. Petersen and C. D. Gutsche, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2942.

CH_3)²¹. Hydrindanones obtained by the oxidation of (31, R = H and CH_3) were also assigned the *trans*-configurations (26, R = H and CH_3).

During a study²² of the cyclization of diethyl β -ethoxycarbonylpimelate (32, R = H), it was observed that treatment of the triester (32, R = H), diethyl β -acetyl- β -ethoxycarbonylpimelate (32, R = $\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_3$), ethyl 2-ethoxycarbonylcyclopentanone-2-acetate (33), and ethyl cyclohexanone-2,3-dicarboxylate (34) with an ethanolic solution of sodium ethoxide (1.1 mole) and also the refluxing of the cyclopentanone derivative (33) with one-quarter mole of sodium ethoxide in ethanol for a prolonged period gave the enolizable cyclopentane β -keto ester (35), isolated by extraction with cold dilute alkali, which on hydrolysis and decarboxylation yielded cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid (36, R = H) characterized through its derivatives. But, treatment of the triester (32, R = H) with sodium or sodium ethoxide in benzene and that of the β -keto ester (33) with sodium ethoxide in benzene or with one-quarter mole of sodium ethoxide in ethanol for a short period gave the enolizable cyclohexane β -keto ester (34) isolated by extraction with alkali, which on hydrolysis and decarboxylation gave cyclohexanone-3-carboxylic acid (37, R = H), also characterized through its derivatives. However, characterization through derivatives of the two keto acids, (36, R = H) and (37, R = H), only identified them as major products in the aforementioned reactions, for the mechanistic interpretation of which the knowledge of the total composition of the products obtained by hydrolysis and decarboxylation was necessary. For this purpose, the products were esterified and IR spectra of the esters were compared with those of authentic methyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate (36, R = CH_3) and methyl cyclohexanone-3-carboxylate (37, R = CH_3) (Fig. 5), and it was immediately revealed that each esterified product was a mixture of the two esters, (36, R = CH_3) and (37, R = CH_3). The intensity distribution in spectral line being Gaussian, the observed intensity, due to overlap of the two lines at 1740 cm^{-1} (cyclopentanone carbonyl) and at 1720 cm^{-1} (cyclohexanone

21. P. Speiser and T. Reichstein, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, **30**, 2143; Pl. A. Plattner, L. Ruzicka, H. Heusser, and E. Angliker, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, **32**, 1517.
22. D. K. Banerjee, J. Dutta and G. Bagavant, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1957, **46A**, 80; D. K. Banerjee and G. Bagavant, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1960, **52A**, 165.

carbonyl) could be uniquely resolved into the two Gaussian curves. On this basis the percentage compositions of the mixtures were calculated, and it was found that in the first case the mixture contained 90% of the cyclopentanone ester (36, R = CH₃) and in the second the mixture contained ca 80% of the cyclohexanone ester (37, R = CH₃). These observations helped us to solve the problem of formation of two different compounds, (35) and (34), as major products under different conditions of cyclization of the triester (32, R = H).

In connection with the synthesis of steroid degradation products, hydrogen cyanide was added on to ethyl 1-cyano-2-methyl-butene-1,3,4-tricarboxylate (38) with λ_{max}^{EtOH} 235 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0), characteristic of an α, β -unsaturated cyanoester chromophore. The UV spectrum of the crude addition product (39) was examined in order to be sure that it was free from the starting compound (38). Surprisingly, the product showed a new absorption band at 247 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.6)²³. Later,²⁴ it was observed that this absorption was characteristic of all saturated compounds having the same dicyanoester moiety. It was also found that while this absorption was shown in alcohol, it was significantly absent in heptane or acetonitrile. Further, intensity of the absorption band decreased with the increase in the concentration of the alcoholic solution. These do not conform to the solvent behaviour of β -keto esters and open chain β -diketones, but are characteristic of cyclic β -diketones²⁵ where chelation

23. D. K. Banerjee, T. R. Kasturi, P. Bagchi, A. R. Sen Gupta and S. K. Das Gupta, *Jour. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1959, *Golden Jubilee Research Volume*, 68.
24. T. R. Kasturi, B. N. Mylari, A. Balasubramanian and C. N. R. Rao, *Canadian J. Chem.*, 1962, **40**, 2272.
25. B. Eistert and W. Reiss, *Chem. Ber.*, 1954, **87**, 92.

is not possible. Inspection of the two possible enolates, (40) and (41), reveals that only the former, where the linear ketenimine group, $-C = C = N-H$, is present and chelation is not possible, can explain the observed solvent behaviour.

In order to prove the mode of enolization, the UV spectra of the tricyano compounds, (42) and (43), the cyano diester (44), the triester (45), and the tetraester (46) were examined²⁶. While the tricyano compounds, (42) and (43), showed UV absorption maxima at $231 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 3.8$) and $231 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon 3.2$) respectively with the same solvent behaviour, the compounds, (44), (45) and (46), where only an ester group could possibly enolize, were transparent in the same region.

The IR spectra (Fig. 6) of (42) and (43) and also that of the corresponding dicyano ester (47), and (48) in chloroform and chloroform-methanol mixture were studied²⁶. It was observed that the chloroform solution showed only the peak for the $C \equiv N$ stretching around 2270 cm^{-1} , whereas in the chloroform-methanol mixture a second peak at $2000-2100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, characteristic of $-C = C = N-$ stretching, appeared along with the nitrile peak, clearly establishing the participation of the cyano group in the enolization. The chloroform-methanol solutions of the dicyano esters, (47) and (48), similarly showed two peaks around 2200 cm^{-1} and 2100 cm^{-1} , while chloroform solution showed a single $C \equiv N$ peak. Furthermore, while in chloroform solution a single $C = O$ stretching band at 1735 cm^{-1} for the ester carbonyl was observable, two peaks at 1745 cm^{-1} and 1720 cm^{-1} were seen in chloroform-methanol solution spectra; the latter peak undoubtedly arises from the conjugated ester carbonyl stretching resulting from ketimination of the cyano group. The influence of the β -cyano group in the ketimination of the α -cyano could be intensified by adding on a second negative group, like $-\text{OCH}_3$, $-\text{CO}_2\text{R}$, and $-\text{CN}$, to the β -carbon atom, as evident from the increase in the extinction coefficients of the same band in the compounds, (49), (50), (51) and (52)²⁶.

26. D. K. Banerjee, T. R. Kasturi, C. N. R. Rao, and A. Srinivasan, unpublished work.

With a view to obtaining dehydroabietic acid (53, R = H) and its methyl ester (53, R = CH₃), the dehydrogenation of abietic acid (54, R = H) and methyl abietate (54, R = CH₃) using tetrachloro-*o*-benzoquinone (55) was studied²⁷. When methyl abietate was

Fig. 6

treated with the quinone (55) in equimolecular proportions, a product was obtained in 41% yield; the use of two moles of the quinone increased the yield to 80%. Elemental analysis showed the presence of a large percentage of chlorine which was retained during vigorous alkaline hydrolysis of the ester to the corresponding acid. On catalytic hydrogenation, both the ester and the acid absorbed two moles of hydrogen each. The physical and spectral characteristics of the ester and the corresponding acid along with those of their tetrahydro derivatives are given in the Table 1. One of the UV absorption maxima, 236 m μ , was the same as that of the starting compound, while the second one, 302 m μ , was significantly close to the UV absorption maximum, 299 m μ , of tetrachlorocatechol. In the tetrahydro compounds the absorption band at 236 m μ , characteristic of the abietadiene system, disappeared, but the band at 302 m μ was retained. The molecular weights of the acid and its tetrahydro-derivative were 544 and 548 respectively, as determined by mass spectrometry, which

happened to be the total of the molecular weights of abietic acid moieties and that of tetra-chlorocatechol minus two hydrogen atoms in each case. The presence of stable chlorine atoms in the molecule, together with the UV data and molecular weights of the product and its tetrahydroderivative strongly suggested that an adduct was formed following the loss of two hydrogen atoms from methyl abietate.

	ADDUCT		TETRAHYDRO	ADDUCT
	ACID	ESTER	ACID	ESTER
MP.	245°	132-136°	145-155°	75-85°
m/e	544		548	
$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{FROM}}$	236 $m\mu$ (ϵ 39,630)	236 $m\mu$ (ϵ 35,810)	302 $m\mu$ (ϵ 2,240)	302 $m\mu$ (ϵ 2,487)
λ_{max}	302 $m\mu$ (ϵ 3,255)	302 $m\mu$ (ϵ 2,877)		
$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{(Nujol)}}$	1698, 1640, 1600, 1548, 1480, 1050, and 806 cm^{-1}	1718, 1640, 1600, 1538, 1428, 1048, and 805 cm^{-1}	1695, 1558, 1420, 1050, and 732 cm^{-1}	1740, 1560, 1420, 1053, and 722 cm^{-1}

Table.1

In the IR spectra of the acid and the ester, 1698 cm^{-1} and 1710 cm^{-1} peaks corresponded to the acid and the ester carbonyl stretchings respectively. Two weak bands at 1640 and 1600 cm^{-1} , indicative of the conjugated diene system, were absent in the tetrahydro derivatives. The strong peaks at 806 cm^{-1} and 805 cm^{-1} , due to the out of plane bending vibrations of the vinyl hydrogen in a trisubstituted olefinic linkage, were also not observable in the spectra of the tetrahydro derivatives. Further, the isopropyl doublet at 1389 and 1369 cm^{-1} present in the spectrum of abietic acid, was significantly absent in the spectra of the acid and the ester and their tetrahydro derivatives, and this indicated modification of the isopropyl group in the abietic acid moiety during the adduct formation and led us to assume dehydrogenation of the isopropyl group by one mole of the quinone (55) to form the conjugated triene (56) as the first step, followed by addition of another mole of the quinone to the isopropylidene group to form the tetrachlorobenzodioxane derivative (57) by one of the mechanisms shown in Fig. 7. Increase in the yield of the adduct from 41% to 80% by increasing one mole of the quinone (55) to two moles for one mole of methyl abietate (54, R = CH₃) supported this assumption.

It may however be observed that in the IR spectra of both (57) and the tetrahydro derivative (58), the normal aromatic skeletal vibration around 1600 cm^{-1} and the =C-O-C (aromatic ether) stretching around 1250 cm^{-1} have experienced considerable shift to lower frequency, viz., 1550 cm^{-1} and 1050 cm^{-1} respectively, presumably due to the influence of the nuclear chlorine atoms in (57) and (58). To confirm these assignments, the IR spectra

(Fig. 8) of tetrachlorocatechol (59, $R = R' = H$), its monomethyl ether (59, $R = H, R' = CH_3$) and dimethyl ether (59, $R = R' = CH_3$) were studied²⁸. The aromatic skeletal vibrations were uniformly showed up at 1550 cm^{-1} in all three compounds. Further, it was observed that the normal C-OH stretching of phenol around 1200 cm^{-1} was shifted to 995 cm^{-1} in tetrachlorocatechol (59, $R = R' = H$). In the monomethyl ether (59, $R = H, R' = CH_3$), strong peaks at 1020 cm^{-1} and 975 cm^{-1} were present, the former being absent in (59, $R = R' = H$). The 975 cm^{-1} peak disappeared in the spectrum of the dimethyl ether (59, $R = R' = CH_3$) which showed only one strong peak at 1020 cm^{-1} , obviously due to the $=C-O-CH_3$ stretching of the aromatic ether. This study clearly established the bathochromic shifts due to the presence of nuclear chlorine atoms.

The peak at 1420 cm^{-1} present in all tetrachlorobenzodioxo compounds is likely to be due to the bathochromic shift suffered by the second aromatic skeletal vibration normally seen around 1500 cm^{-1} .

In the NMR spectrum of the adduct acid the three equally narrow 3H singlets at 48.5, 74, and 87.5 Hz could be assigned to C-4b angular methyl, C-8 axial methyl, and a methyl group attached to a carbon carrying an oxygen atom or to an olefinic carbon; however, narrowness of the signal decided the assignment in favour of the former. The signals for the corresponding methyl groups in the tetrahydro derivative were observed at 67.5, 73.5, and 77.5 Hz. The downfield shift of C-4b methyl signal on hydrogenation might be due to the removal of long range shielding by the Δ^{10} -double bond. Similarly, removal of the deshielding effect of the Δ^1 -double bond on the isopropyl methyl by hydrogenation is observed by the upfield shift of the corresponding signal. The well resolved AB quartet centred at 259 Hz (JAB = 11.5 Hz) for the magnetically non-equivalent methylene protons could be assigned to the benzoxymethylene group attached to the asymmetric centre. Two vinyl proton signals, a broad multiplet at 332.5 Hz (1H) and a singlet 365 Hz (1H), were easily assignable to C-10 and C-1 hydrogens respectively. That the latter signal was not due to the phenolic proton resonance at 365.6 Hz shown by tetrachlorocatechol monomethyl ether was proved by the persistence of these two signals in the adduct even after exchange with D_2O and by their disappearance in the spectrum of the tetrahydro derivative. Thus the structures, (57) and (58), assigned to the adduct and its tetrahydro derivative respectively were thoroughly proved.

Following the establishment of the structure of the adduct, investigation²⁹ on its conversion to methyl 13-methoxydeisopropyldehydroabietate (60) was undertaken. For this purpose, conversion of the adduct (57) to Δ^{18} -dehydroabietic acid or its ester (61) appeared to be very necessary. But, usual chemical methods proved to be unsuccessful. The mass spectrum of the adduct revealed the formation of a triene radical ion (62) by fragmentation (Fig. 9), with the elimination of tetrachloro-*o*-benzoquinone. In view of the high intensity of this peak, we thought that it might be possible to simulate this fragmentation by heating, although energy involved in this case would be far less than 50-60 eV associated with the bombarding electron beam in mass spectrometry. It was also expected that the unstable intermediate product might get dehydrogenated by tetrachloro-*o*-benzoquinone and readily stabilised by aromatisation. Actually, by heating the adduct ester (57, R = CH_3), there was obtained a mixture of methyl dehydroabietate (53, R = CH_3) and methyl Δ^{18} -dehydroabietate (61, R = CH_3), besides tetrachlorocatechol. The compound (61, R = CH_3),

which predominated in the mixture, could then be converted into (60) through a short sequence of reactions.

In a stereoselective synthesis³⁰ of the *cis*, *trans*- C-11 Acid (67), a degradation product of Agathic Acid, it was necessary to check the conformation of several intermediates obtained through a sequence of reactions shown below, and this was possible through the study of their NMR spectra.

In the NMR spectrum (Fig. 9) of methyl 2-acetyl-2-cyano-1-methylcyclohexanecarboxylate (63) the total width (25 Hz) of the quintet centred at 171.5 Hz, assigned to the C-3 proton, being larger than that of the same proton in the NMR spectrum (Fig. 10) of its ketal (64), indicated an axial orientation. The coupling constant (5 Hz) of the doublet at 212 Hz ascribed to the C-2 proton, being in accord with axial-equatorial coupling involving protons attached to carbon atoms bearing electronegative substituents, implied an equatorial orientation. These inferences, along with a study of the changes in chemical shifts and coupling constants observed (Fig. 10) on ketalisation of the keto nitrile led to the assignment of the conformation (63) to it. The smaller total width (15 Hz) of the poorly resolved multiplet centred at 186 Hz, assignable to the C-3 proton of the ketal nitrile ester (64), compared to that of the same proton in the parent ketone (63), proved its equatorial orientation. The C-2 proton of (64) which showed a doublet ($J = 5$ Hz) at 144 Hz, characteristic of axial-equatorial coupling, was therefore assigned axial orientation. This reversal of orientations at C-2 and C-3 on ketalisation suggested ring-flipping (Fig. 11) and led to the assignment of conformation (64) which avoided the energetically unfavourable axial conformation for the ketal group, comparable in bulk to a *t*-butyl group. This was further supported by the deshielding (14.5 Hz) of the C-3 proton, because of the change from the axial to the equatorial

30. D. K. Banerjee, S. N. Balasubrahmanyam and R. Ranganathan, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1966, 1458.

orientation and the additional shielding (24.5 Hz) of the C-2 proton, ascribed to the change not only from the equatorial to the axial orientation but also from the diequatorial to the diaxial relationship with the nitrile group. Consequent on ring-flipping, deshielding of the C-1 methyl group by the nitrile group might be expected, as the two would be brought to the 1,3-diaxial relationship. Assignment of the peak at 88 Hz to the C-1 methyl would amount to a deshielding of 16 Hz, which is of the same order as that observed in the case of 6 β -cyano steroids. The assignment of the peak at 76 Hz to the C-7 methyl group implied shielding to the extent of 63.5 Hz, which is 22 Hz more than that observed for the corresponding change in the methylated series. This extra shielding has been ascribed to the ring transformation. The NMR spectrum (Fig. 12) of the methylated ketal nitrile ester (65) showed the C-2 proton resonance as a singlet at 135 Hz, in contrast to the doublet for the same proton in the precursor (64), and provided strong evidence for methylation at C-3; the shielding (9 Hz) of this proton was attributed to the newly formed methyl group. No significant shift was noticed in the position of the C-1 methyl peak, indicative of unaltered orientation of the nitrile group on methylation. This confirmed the conformation of the methylated compound (65). The splitting into a quartet (A_2B_2) of the dioxolan methylene resonance, the shielding (7 Hz) of these protons, and the deshielding (15 Hz) of the C-7 methyl group could be ascribed to the hindrance to free rotation about the C-2—C-7 bond as a result of greater overcrowding in the molecule due to methylation.

The effect of the aforementioned overcrowding was also observable in the UV spectrum (Fig. 15) of the methylated keto nitrile ester (66), obtained by deketalisation of (65). While the unmethylated keto nitrile ester (63) showed only the normal absorption at 278 $m\mu$ (ϵ 28) in ethanol, the compound (66) showed λ_{max}^{EtOH} 213 (ϵ 1527), 257–259 (ϵ 84), and inflexion at 287 $m\mu$ (ϵ 42). The two bands occurring at lower wave lengths, besides the highest wavelength band due to the normal $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, were probably due to an interaction between the π -clouds of the acetyl and the nitrile groups brought into greater proximity

Fig.9

Fig.10

following methylation. One interesting feature of these bands was that they paralleled those for *trans*-cyclodec-5-en-1-one (Fig. 15). That this interaction involves only the excited state was evident from the normal IR spectrum of the molecule.

Fig. 11

Fig. 12

Fig. 13

OBSERVED CHANGES IN CHEMICAL SHIFTS + DESHIELDING
- SHIELDING

Proton	Ketalisation (63) → (64)	Methylation (64) → (65)	De-ketalisation (65) → (66)	(63) → (66)
CH ₃ -C ₁	+16.0 CPS	+3.0 CPS	-5 or -10.5 CPS	+14.0 CPS
H-C ₂	-68.5	-9.0	+43.5	-33.5
H-C ₃	+14.5	-	-	-
-CO ₂ CH ₃	-7.5	0.0	+9.0	+1.5

Fig. 14

Comparison of the NMR spectrum (Fig. 12) of the methylated ketal (65) and that (Fig. 13) of the corresponding ketone (66) revealed that de-ketalisation resulted in the shielding (5 and 10 Hz) of the methyl groups at C-1 and C-3, attributable to the release of overcrowding. The deshielding (9 Hz) of the ester methyl group might be due to the removal of the shielding influence of the C-O bonds of the dioxolan group, a smaller effect being observable in the non-methylated series.

Solvent	Wavelength in $m\mu$
Alcohol	213(152), 257-259(84), Inflexion 287(42)
Acetonitrile	Inflexion 251-253(48.4), 283-285(40.7)
Dioxan	Inflexion 249-250(50.9), Inflexion 280-286(39.3)
Cyclohexane	254-255(54.4), 286(33.9)

trans-
214.5, 260, and 302 $m\mu$
(2300) (423) (73)

cis-
299.9 $m\mu$
(15)

Direct comparison (Fig. 14) of the NMR spectra (Fig. 9 and 13) of the keto nitrile ester (63) and the corresponding methylated compound (66) highlights the environmental changes on methylation and supported our conformational assignments. The resulting 1,3-diaxial relationship of the C-1 methyl and C-3 nitrile groups deshielded the former by 14 Hz. The large upfield shift (33.5 Hz) of the C-2 proton was ascribed to (i) the change from the equatorial to the axial orientation, (ii) the change from the diequatorial to the diaxial relationship with the nitrile group, and (iii) the shielding influence of the newly formed C-3 methyl bond. The C-7 methyl was also shielded (9 Hz), indicating a change of environment. The methylated keto nitrile was therefore assigned the conformation (66) and the C-11 Acid, derived from it, the configuration (67) with the identical conformation.

We had also earlier achieved the synthesis of the isomeric C-11 Acid, obtained by degradation of abietic acid, for the first time, but a rigorous proof in favour of its *trans*, *meso* configuration was not provided. Comparison of the NMR spectra (Fig. 16 and 17) of the methyl esters of the isomeric acids, however, proved their configurational assignments. The identical environments due to a *meso* configuration of the two C-methyl groups and also that of the two equatorial tertiary methoxycarbonyl groups were shown by single sharp peaks at 118 and 364 Hz respectively; the peak at 367 Hz with half the intensity of the latter was attributable only to the secondary methoxycarbonyl group. In contrast, non-equivalence of the chemical environments of the two C-methyl groups and the three methoxycarbonyl groups in the *cis*, *trans* isomer was demonstrated by two sharp singlets at 117 and 119 Hz for C-methyl groups and by three peaks at 364, 367, and 370 Hz for the methoxycarbonyl groups, all of equal intensity. Occurrence of the first two peaks at identical positions (364 and 367 Hz) in the two cases permitted their being assigned to the equatorial C-1 (tertiary) and C-2 (secondary) methoxycarbonyl groups; the new resonance at 370 Hz in the *cis*, *trans* case must therefore be due to the axial C-3 (tertiary) methoxycarbonyl. The C-2 methoxycarbonyl in this isomer was proved to be equatorial. Therefore the C-2 methoxycarbonyl in the *meso* isomer should also be equatorial, confirming its *trans*-, *meso* configuration.

The multiplet centred at 231 Hz in the spectrum (Fig. 17) of the *cis, trans* isomer was attributable to the axial C-5 proton deshielded by the axial C-3 methoxycarbonyl, the effect being absent in the spectrum (Fig. 16) of the other isomer. The deshielding (35 Hz) of the C-2 proton in the *trans, meso* isomer with respect to the same proton in the other isomer was also in accord with its configuration. The foregoing constituted unequivocal proof for the *trans, meso* configuration of the abietic acid degradation product.

Fig.16

Fig.17